

Consumer Behavior: A Young Generation Purchase Decision Model

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the model of purchasing decisions in the younger generation in purchasing bottled water products, this is done because of the need for ongoing research to explain models of consumer behavior through measuring consumer purchasing decisions. This research was conducted using a quantitative descriptive analysis approach with a total sample of 100 samples, data analysis was carried out in several stages, namely data instrument analysis, classical assumption detection, hypothesis testing and R-Square determination test to find out how much influence the overall variables used in representing buying decision.

The results of the study found that brand image had no significant effect on purchasing decisions, promotion and trust had a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, service quality had a significant and negative effect on purchasing decisions. The results of this study can contribute to economics as a literature study on purchasing decision models for the younger generation.

Keywords:- *Buying Decision; Brand Image; Promotion; Service Quality; Trust;*

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable economic development is one of the results of a good governance system, the government has clear policies and contributions in synergy to carry out economic development. The entire corporate sector, both public and private, always strives to improve internal operations and effective strategies in dealing with internal business competition[26]. The existence of a retail business is a type of business that has good opportunities from time to time, along with the development of science and technology, the type of business in the retail sector is getting better and of better quality in terms of service and income. However, in its development, not all types of businesses in the retail sector have the same opportunity to develop, in fact, there are several businesses in the retail sector that have gone out of business or are experiencing bankruptcy[5].

The problem is due to the low demand for products from consumers. Companies must think about strategic steps to avoid factors that can cause a person to lose interest in making a purchase decision. Purchasing decisions are one of the main priorities that must be made by a company in order to form an increased consumer surplus[3]. The company's behavior above will have an impact on increasing the number of operations

which have an impact on increasing the number of consumer requests.

Companies must pay attention to purchasing decisions made by consumers so that the growth stage of a company's product can experience an increase[14]. Several factors can influence consumer purchases, one of which is brand image. A good brand image that can be accepted by consumers will drive consumer purchasing decisions[19]. Meanwhile, a bad brand image in the eyes of consumers can reduce consumer interest in making purchasing decisions, therefore companies must maintain and improve the brand image of each product to consumers[13]. Brand image is an alternative determinant of purchasing a product by consumers so that the product introduction stage must be balanced with the product's brand image[23].

The introduction stage of a product must be balanced with promotion, so that promotion carried out by a company becomes one of the media for consumers to find out about a company's products[4]. Better promotions will have a positive impact on increasing consumer purchasing decisions[8]. Meanwhile, promotions that are getting worse will have a negative impact on consumer purchasing decisions[34]. Promotion can be said as a medium of information to consumers directly based on product quality[18]. Companies must maintain continuity of promotions as an effort to stimulate consumer knowledge about these products and have an impact on consumer purchasing decisions[28].

One form of customer satisfaction can be done by providing services to consumers, service quality is a factor that must be considered and carried out by companies to consumers[22]. Consumers will feel their own satisfaction with the products consumed based on the services provided by the company[38]. Good service quality will encourage consumer purchasing decisions, while services that are not optimal at the company will reduce consumer interest in making purchasing decisions[9]. Thus the company always provides quality service and always evaluates the services provided to consumers[16]. Good service quality must always be improved by the company in maintaining consumer loyalty to the product[33].

Consumer trust in products is one of the factors that must be maintained by companies, companies that are able to maintain consumer trust will be able to encourage consumer decisions in purchasing products[2]. If the company cannot maintain consumer confidence in its products, it will have a negative impact on lower consumer purchasing decisions[20].

Consumers will think again in making purchasing decisions, so there is a need for strategic steps in maintaining consumer confidence in the products offered by the company[7]. Strong consumer confidence in a product will create consumer loyalty to the product so that there is no substitute for it when the product is no longer circulating in the community[15].

Kotler said that buying decisions made by buyers are actually a collection of a number of decisions[22]. High consumer purchasing decisions can result in high sales volume so that the profits to be obtained by the company are higher[18]. In order for companies to achieve high profits, companies must take into account consumer purchasing decisions for these goods/services[35]. If a company can influence consumers to make purchasing decisions and can analyze consumers in compiling product/service quality, price, influence of advertising/promotions and so on, then in competition the company can excel and can also be profitable for the company itself[21].

Several previous studies have shown a relationship between brand image, promotion, service and consumer trust in product purchasing decisions. The update in this research is to examine further the relationship between brand image, promotion, service and consumer trust in product purchasing decisions. This research was conducted with the aim of building and providing an integrated research model in the scope of consumer behavior as a basis that can describe quantitatively the relationship between brand image, promotion, service and consumer trust in product purchasing decisions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Buying Decision

Kotler said that the purchase decision made by the buyer is actually a collection of a number of decisions[27]. High consumer purchasing decisions can result in high sales volume so that the profits to be obtained by the company are higher[8]. In order for companies to achieve high profits, companies must take into account consumer purchasing decisions for these goods/services[35].

B. Service Quality

Service quality is the customer's perception of the totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that depend on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs[9]. Service, is an action taken to meet the needs of other people (consumers, customers, clients, guests, etc.) whose level of satisfaction can only be felt by the person serving or being served[11].

C. Trust

The higher consumer trust, the higher the level of consumer buying interest. Trust needs to exist when deciding to order products and when consumers send financial information and other personal data in making transactions[32]. Trust is a condition when one of the parties involved in the exchange process believes in the reliability and integrity of the other party. Trust is the willingness or

willingness to rely on a partner involved in a trusted exchange. Willingness is the result of the belief that the parties involved in the exchange will provide consistent quality, honesty, responsibility, service and good heart. This belief will create a close relationship between the parties involved in the exchange[3].

D. Brand Image

Brand image is a representation of the overall perception of the brand and is formed from information and knowledge about the brand[29]. Brand image is related to attitudes in the form of beliefs and preferences for a brand. Consumers who have a positive image of a brand will be more likely to make a purchase[29].

Brand image is a collection of memories that exist in the minds of consumers about a brand, both positive and negative. A positive brand image provides benefits for producers to be better known by consumers, in other words consumers will make their choice to buy products that have a good brand image. Vice versa, if the brand image is negative, consumers tend to consider it more when buying a product[30].

E. Promotion

Promotion is any form of communication used to inform, persuade or remind people about products produced by organizations, individuals or households[25]. There are several reasons marketers carry out promotions, namely: providing information, stimulating demand, differentiating products, reminding current customers, reminding customers about the advantages of a company's products can prevent them from switching to competitors when they decide to replace or improve their products, the Promotional competitor block can be used to facing competitors' marketing efforts to counter their advertising campaigns, responding to negative news sometimes the competition does not sell similar products and other companies. Often companies fall victim to publicity and fakes[25].

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research approach was carried out using quantitative methods with a quantitative descriptive analysis approach. The source of the data in this study was a questionnaire distributed by the researcher with various systematics and methods of continuous distribution, while the type of data in this study was primary data obtained directly from the respondents. The data collection method in this study was carried out directly based on the research concept framework, namely the respondents who were selected directly filled out the questionnaire given by the researcher. The population is a population whose number cannot be known, so the researchers used a sampling technique, namely purposive sampling and the number of samples in this study was 100 samples.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following are the results of data analysis to determine the effect of brand image, promotion, service quality and trust on purchasing decisions. Following are the results of data analysis through validity tests:

TABLE 1. VALIDITY TEST RESULTS

Indicator	r- Table	r-Count	Conclusion
Y1.1	0.1654	0.210	Valid data
Y1.2	0.1654	0.196	Valid data
Y1.3	0.1654	0.502	Valid data
Y1.4	0.1654	0.378	Valid data
Y1.5	0.1654	0.716	Valid data
X1.1	0.1654	0.543	Valid data
X1.2	0.1654	0.501	Valid data
X1.3	0.1654	0.570	Valid data
X2.1	0.1654	0.684	Valid data
X2.2	0.1654	0.502	Valid data
X2.3	0.1654	0.378	Valid data
X2.4	0.1654	0.314	Valid data
X3.1	0.1654	0.683	Valid data
X3.2	0.1654	0.650	Valid data
X3.3	0.1654	0.213	Valid data
X3.4	0.1654	0.680	Valid data
X3.5	0.1654	0.695	Valid data
X4.1	0.1654	0.617	Valid data
X4.2	0.1654	0.793	Valid data
X4.3	0.1654	0.629	Valid data
X4.4	0.1654	0.664	Valid data

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the calculated r value is greater than the r table value. So it can be explained that the validity test in this study was fulfilled. While the results of data analysis on the reliability test showed that the Cronbach's alpha value of 0.889 was greater than 0.60. Thus it can be concluded that the reliability test in this study was fulfilled. Following are the results of the normality test in this study:

FIG 1. NORMALITY TEST RESULTS

Based on the picture above it can be explained that these points are close to the diagonal line, so it can be explained that the regression model meets the assumption of normality.

The linearity test is determined to determine the linear relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Following are the results of the linearity test in this study:

TABLE 2. LINEARITY TEST RESULTS

Variable Relations	Linearity Value
Brand image → Purchase decision	0,000
Promotion → Purchase decision	0,000
Service quality → Purchase decision	0,000
Trust → Purchase decision	0,000

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the indicators to measure the level of linearity in this study are carried out through values on linearity. The linearity value of 0.000 is smaller than the significance level. So it can be concluded that the linearity test on the variables used in the study is fulfilled.

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test it can be explained that the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient shows a value of less than 0.8, these results explain that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in this study. The following are the results of the multicollinearity test analysis.

TABLE 4. MULTICOLLINEARITY TEST RESULTS

	Buying decision	Brand Image	Promotion	Quality of service	Trust
Buying decision	1.000	0.430	0.729	0.410	0.551
Brand Image	0.430	1.000	0.529	0.523	0.482
Promotion	0.729	0.529	1.000	0.594	0.574
Quality of service	0.410	0.523	0.594	1.000	0.625
Trust	0.551	0.482	0.574	0.625	1.000

From the table above it can be explained that the value between the variables above is less than 0.8 so that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in this study. Following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test:

FIG 2. HETEROSCEDASTICITY TEST RESULTS

Based on the picture above it can be explained that there is no specific pattern because the points spread irregularly above and below the 0 axis on the Y axis. So it can be concluded that there were no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in this study. Following are the results of partial data analysis:

TABLE 5. RESULTS OF PARTIAL ANALYSIS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	10.866	0.916	-	11.859	0.000
Brand Image	0.066	0.083	0.063	0.788	0.432
Promotion	0.575	0.074	0.667	7.816	0.000
Quality of service	-0.309	0.089	-0.415	-3.469	0.001
Trust	0.384	0.093	0.480	4.144	0.000

Based on the table above it can be explained that a constant value of 10.866 explains that if the variables brand image, promotion, service quality and trust are not applied then the purchase decision value is 10.866.

Brand image has no significant effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.432 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05.

Promotion has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient value of 0.575. The beta coefficient value of 0.575 indicates that an increase in promotion per unit will increase the purchase decision by 0.575.

Service quality has a significant and negative effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.001 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient value of -0.309. The beta coefficient value of -0.309 indicates that an increase in service quality per unit will reduce purchasing decisions by -0.309.

Trust has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient value of 0.384. The beta coefficient value of 0.384 indicates that an increase in trust by one unit will increase the purchase decision by 0.384.

Meanwhile, based on the results of tests carried out simultaneously, it can be explained that the significance value is 0.000. So it can be concluded that brand image, promotion, service quality and trust influence purchasing decisions together.

The R-Square test is conducted to find out how much the dependent variable represents the independent variable or is done to find out how much the variables in this study represent purchasing decisions. Based on the results of the analysis of the Adjusted R Square value of 0.591, it can be concluded that the variables brand image, promotion, service quality and trust are able to represent purchasing decisions by 59.1% while the remaining 40.9%. purchasing decisions are influenced by other variables not discussed in this study.

A. Brand image influences product purchasing decisions

The results of this study concluded that brand image had no significant effect on purchasing decisions, the results of the analysis showed a significance value of 0.432 which was greater than the significance level of 0.05. This shows that brand image has no effect on the purchasing decisions of younger generations of consumers to buy Indomart bottled water products. Based on the results of data analysis, it can be seen that the purchasing decisions made by the younger generation do not see the brand image of the product, this can happen because the Indomart product brand is already attached to consumers so that the existence of a brand image does not have an impact on purchasing decisions.

Several factors can influence consumer purchases, one of which is brand image. A good brand image that can be accepted by consumers will drive consumer purchasing decisions[19]. Meanwhile, a bad brand image in the eyes of consumers can reduce consumer interest in making purchasing decisions, therefore companies must maintain and improve the brand image of each product to consumers[13]. Brand image is an alternative determinant of purchasing a product by consumers so that the product introduction stage must be balanced with the product's brand image[23].

Consumers in choosing product brands will go through the trial stage first, at this stage consumers will often try various brands[25]. If the brand feels suitable and fulfills what is expected from similar products, consumers will continue to look for that brand[6]. A brand or mark is a name, term, sign, design symbol or a combination thereof which identifies the product or service produced by a company[1]. Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded that hypothesis 1a in this study is not accepted, which is indicated by brand image which has no significant effect on purchasing decisions.

B. Promotion influences product purchasing decisions

Based on the results of the study it can be explained that promotion has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient value of 0.575. The beta coefficient value of 0.575 indicates that an increase in promotion per unit will increase the purchase decision by 0.575. Thus it can be concluded that promotions are able to influence purchasing decisions for Indomaret brand bottled water products for the younger generation, the increasing promotions carried out by companies will increase product purchasing decisions.

Promotion carried out by a company becomes one of the media for consumers to find out about a company's products[4]. Better promotions will have a positive impact on increasing consumer purchasing decisions[8]. Meanwhile, promotions that are getting worse will have a negative impact on consumer purchasing decisions[34]. Promotion can be said as a medium of information to consumers directly based on product quality[18]. Companies must maintain continuity of promotions as an effort to stimulate consumer knowledge about these products and have an impact on consumer purchasing decisions[28].

Explains that promotion is any form of communication used to inform, persuade or remind people about products produced by organizations, individuals or households[18]. Promotion is a marketing variable that can be used by consumers as a reference in choosing the desired goods/services[8]. If consumers are interested in using the product/service being promoted, it will generate market demand, conversely if consumers have never heard of it and are not sure about the product/service being promoted, it will not generate demand[37]. Promotion is also a determinant of the success of the company. In a good marketing program, a strategic development framework is needed to formulate an effective marketing strategy so that companies can penetrate the target market so that they can achieve predetermined sales targets[10]. Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded that hypothesis 1b in this study is accepted, which is indicated by promotion having a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions.

C. Quality of service influences product purchasing decisions

Based on the results of data analysis, it can be explained that service quality has a significant and negative effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.001 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient value of -0.309. The beta coefficient value of -0.309 indicates that an increase in service quality per unit will reduce purchasing decisions by -0.309. Thus it can be concluded that the quality of service performed by company employees has an impact on reducing the level of purchasing decisions. purchase.

One form of customer satisfaction can be done by providing services to consumers, service quality is a factor that must be considered and carried out by companies to consumers[22]. Consumers will feel their own satisfaction with the products consumed based on the services provided by the company[38]. Good service quality will encourage consumer purchasing decisions, while services that are not optimal at the company will reduce consumer interest in making purchasing decisions[9]. Thus the company always provides quality service and always evaluates the services provided to consumers[16]. Good service quality must always be improved by the company in maintaining consumer loyalty to the product[33].

Service quality is an action or activity that can be offered by one party to another, which is basically intangible and does not result in ownership[24]. The company's ability to provide services to consumers can become a company's profit center[11]. Service is any activity or benefit offered by one party to another that is intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything. Service production can be related to physical production or not[31]. Based on the results of the above research it can be concluded that hypothesis 1c in this study is not accepted which is indicated by the quality of service has a significant and negative effect on purchasing decisions.

D. Trust influences product purchasing decisions

Based on the results of data analysis it can be explained that trust has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, this is indicated by a significance value of 0.000 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 with a coefficient value of 0.384. The beta coefficient value of 0.384 indicates that an increase in trust by one unit will increase the purchase decision by 0.384. Thus it can be concluded that trust is one of the determining factors in making purchasing decisions for Indomaret bottled drinking water products in the younger generation. This can be done by companies in increasing consumer purchases made by the younger generation. An increase in purchasing decisions is offset by an increase in consumer confidence in the product to be purchased.

Consumer trust in products is one of the factors that must be maintained by companies, companies that are able to maintain consumer trust will be able to encourage consumer decisions in purchasing products[2]. If the company cannot maintain consumer confidence in its products, it will have a negative impact on lower consumer purchasing decisions[20]. Consumers will think again in making purchasing decisions, so there is a need for strategic steps in maintaining consumer confidence in the products offered by the company[7]. Strong consumer confidence in a product will create consumer loyalty to the product so that there is no substitute for it when the product is no longer circulating in the community[15].

Low customer confidence in making purchases is caused by feelings of doubt about the quality of the products purchased[34]. Customers feel afraid if the goods purchased are not as expected, therefore the trust factor in purchasing goods is still a serious problem that needs to be considered by the seller, this factor is important in influencing the shopping process carried out by consumers[28]. Trust is a business pillar, where building and creating consumers is one of the most important factors in creating customer loyalty[34]. Trust arises when those involved have received guarantees from other parties, in this case testimonials from a product that has been purchased[31]. Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded that hypothesis 1d in this study is accepted, which is indicated by trust having a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research above, it can be concluded that brand image has no significant effect on purchasing decisions, promotion and trust have a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, service quality has a significant and negative effect on purchasing decisions. Based on the results of the research it can be explained that the suggestions in this study include companies being able to increase purchasing decisions and repurchase intentions by increasing promotions and consumer confidence, it is necessary to carry out further research on service quality and brand image. Respondents observed in this study were more public and not only focused on the younger generation.

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